

Helix Nebula – The Science Cloud

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Abstract: This document outlines the three main events where the pilot services resulting from the PCP project have been showcased. Dedicated training sessions, to target the requirements of researchers, technology leaders, experts and novices, have been arranged to provide an update about the current status of the project, and learn how vouchers can be used to promote the adoption of pilot services for limited scale usage. During the last event, at CERN, the solution proposed by EGI to support the long-tail of science users with the HNSciCloud vouchers has been introduced.

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Executive Summary

This document reports on the three main events where the pilot services resulting from the PCP project have been showcased to end-users, developers and system administrators. Overall, these events aimed to promote the solutions and reach a wider plethora of users and demonstrate the tangible benefits in adopting the innovative cloud services developed by the contractors in the context of the PCP project.

The present document is organized as follows:

- Section 1 introduces a series of events hosted at HNSciCloud procurers' premises, or during international conferences, where the pilot services resulting from the HNSciCloud Pre-Commercial Procurement project have been presented.
- Section 2 reports the demonstration of the HNSciCloud pilot services during these events. Overall, the training sessions aimed at providing an update about the current status of the project and of the high-level solutions developed in the framework of the project. To promote the pilot services, during the training sessions one half day was fully dedicated to the organisation of a public session to provide all users, and potential newcomers, with an overview of the most relevant services developed in the framework of the project (e.g. Onedata, the global data access solution to transparently access data distributed across different data centres). Before the end of the pilot phase, users started to use vouchers for promoting the adoption of pilot services for limited scale usage. The vouchers solutions developed in the framework of the project have been also used by EGI to support the long-tail of science users. The first integration of the HNSciCloud vouchers in the EGI eco-system has been reported in November during the final event which marks the end of the pilot phase. The integration of the HNSciCloud vouchers in the EOSC Marketplace will be finalized early next year.
- Section 3 draws some conclusions about the training sessions and dissemination events organized by the project during the second part of the pilot phase.

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1. Introduction

During the pilot phase of the HNSciCloud PCP project, RHEA Group and T-Systems demonstrated the resulting pilot services in a series of training events hosted at HNSciCloud procurers' premises in Europe or during international conferences. The execution and demonstration of use-cases identified by the Buyers Group, on the implemented pilot platforms, contributed to assessing the acceptability of the procured services.

Dedicated training sessions and live demos have been organized during the following events:

- HNSciCloud session at CHEP 2018 conference in Sofia (09-13 June 2018).
- The HNSciCloud session at GridKA School in Karlsruhe (28 August 2018).
- The HNSciCloud session at CERN during the end of the pilot phase (28-30 November 2018).

2. Demonstration of the pilot services

The demonstration performed at the three main events are described below.

2.1.1. CHEP 2018 Conference

The CHEP 2018¹ conference, organized in Sofia, Bulgaria (09-13 July 2018), was a world-wide premiere for commercial providers to demonstrate how the pilot services developed during the course of the project can help researchers to do more and better research and, as consequence, providing an innovative vision of how to develop capacity necessary to support the nascent European Open Science Cloud (EOSC) – the digital research space for Europe's 1.8 million researchers.

From a technical perspective, RHEA Group and T-Systems contributed to the event with two keynotes to showcase how the hybrid cloud developed by the HNSciCloud Pre-Commercial Procurement (PCP) project can support high-performance and data-intensive scientific use-cases. In these keynotes, the two contractors highlighted how:

- large-scale data can be processed at new performance levels with hundreds of containers and,
- how data can be processed in an intelligent manner making use of Onedata, the Data Management solution adopted by the two commercial providers to enable the sharing of data across multiple cloud infrastructures as if they are stored in their local file-

¹ <http://chep2018.org/>

system in an efficient way using standard protocols such as: POSIX, REST, OAI-PMH, HTTP, etc.

Additional key points offered by the innovative service pilots are:

- the transparent support to the eduGAIN and Elixir AAI identity federations which provide users with seamless access to cloud resources over the GÉANT network via web browser, APIs and CLI, and
- the possibility to use cloud-based broker solutions and OpenStack and S3-compatible tools to facilitate the execution and management of scientific applications.

2.1.2. GridKa School 2018

The International GridKa School 2018², organized by the Karlsruhe Institute of Technology (KIT) (27-31 August 2018), was a good opportunity for researchers, technology leaders, experts and novices to:

- receive an update about the current status of the project and learn about the voucher schemes developed by the HNSciCloud contractors to promote the adoption of the HNSciCloud pilot services for limited scale usage, and
- gain practical experiences on knowledge sharing and information exchange.

The event was attended by RHEA and T-Systems who contributed with lectures and practical hands-on sessions during which student followed a tutorial to deploy simple applications making use of the pilot platform services.

2.1.3. M-PIL-3.4 event

During the pilot phase the two contractors developed voucher schemes by which vouchers can be distributed to end-users selected by the Buyers Group to encourage the uptake of the pilot platform services for limited scale usage. As already described in the D6.1 – Best Practices Report, the voucher scheme proposed by the two commercial contractors addresses the following key points:

1. Each voucher should have a validity of one year from the data of issue and can be redeemable against any service included in the contractor's pilot platform.
2. A total of 100 vouchers of a values of 250 euros each would be sufficient for the Buyers Group.
3. The Buyers Group will identify the users entitled to access the pilot services.

² <http://gridka-school.scc.kit.edu/2018/>

4. It essential that consumption is automatically blocked as soon as the voucher credit is exhausted.
5. Vouchers have been proposed to encourage the uptake of HNSciCloud pilot services by the long tail of science users.

Starting from the second pilot phase progress review (M-PIL-3.2) the Infrastructure Manager (IM)³ framework and the Elastic Cloud Computing Cluster (EC3)⁴ portal developed by the Universitat Politècnica de València (UPV)⁵ have been further extended in order to allow “long tail of science” users to access resources provided by the EGI Federation, partner institutions, and commercial cloud providers involved in the HNSciCloud PCP pilot phase. In the course of the years, EGI has well-established processes to allocate resources for user communities organized in structured Virtual Organizations (VOs), these involve a procedure for engaging user community with the EGI service providers, and resulting in medium-term service allocations. Unfortunately these processes are not suitable for individual researchers and small research teams as they may involve:

- Obtaining an IGTF⁶ personal certificate;
- Set-up a virtual organization (VO) or join an existing one after approval;
- Have the VO enabled in the distributed infrastructure, and use the resources.

Recognising the need for simpler and more harmonized access to the computational resources for such users, EGI in the context of the EGI-Engage project, started to develop a new service. The Applications on Demand (AoD) service⁷, which debuted in April 2017, connects cloud, HTC, science gateways and application services from NGIs and other partners, and makes them accessible via a Marketplace. The integration of the HNSciCloud pilot platform services with the EGI AoD service will offer new opportunities for users to perform data-intensive simulations on large, distributed network of computing resources.

2.1.3.1. How vouchers can support the long tail of science users

In this section we describe how “long of tail science” users can easily discover the EGI Applications on Demand (AoD) service published in the EOSC portal Marketplace and submit a service-order request to deploy a virtual cluster on the HNSciCloud pilot services. The

³ <http://www.grycap.upv.es/im/index.php>

⁴ <http://servproject.i3m.upv.es/ec3/>

⁵ <https://www.upv.es/index-en.html>

⁶ Interoperable Global Trust Federation: <https://www.igtf.net/>

⁷ <https://www.egi.eu/services/applications-on-demand/>

virtual cluster will be deployed and configured with the requested software packages using the Elastic Cloud Compute Cluster (EC3)⁸ portal.

The procedure to submit a service-order request through the ESOC Marketplace is the following:

- The starting point for the user to deploy a virtual cluster on the HNSciCloud pilot services is represented by the EOSC Marketplace, a single entry point where the user can navigate the EOSC service catalogue, discover a service of interest, get information about it, and place an order in a few clicks by specifying the service requested along with the quantity, the quality and the duration. The EOSC Marketplace is publicly accessible at <https://marketplace.eosc-portal.eu/> and is currently operated by Cyfronet. The back-end is connected to a Jira ticketing system through which service-order requests can be tracked and distributed to providers.
- After the user lands on the EOSC Marketplace webpage, through the search menu, he/she can discover the advanced services they need for their work. All the available services are grouped in 8 main categories. No authentication is required to browse and discover the list of services published in the marketplace.
- The user selects the Elastic Cloud Compute Cluster (EC3) platform and submits a service request to access to one or more applications available in the Elastic Cloud Compute Cluster (EC3) portal by clicking on the “Request Access” button.
- To deploy the virtual cluster on the HNSciCloud pilot services, the voucher checkbox has to be enabled. The submission of a service order request with the voucher check-box enabled triggers a dedicated procedure that the operators of the EGI Applications on Demand service have to follow in order to fulfil the user’s request.
- Click on “Add to Cart” button to add the selected application in the shopping cart.
- When the application is in the shopping cart the user can click on the “Proceed to checkout” button to submit the order, or on the “Continue shopping” button if he/she wants to add more applications to the cart.
- The Shopping-cart summary shows the application(s) requested by the user.
- To proceed with the service order, the user is invited to provide additional information for profiling the order (e.g. the motivation for requesting the Service, etc.) The profiling of the service request requires the user to be logged into the Marketplace.
- Login to the EOSC Marketplace. Two options are allowed: the user can access with his/her personal academic credentials or use the EGI Single Sign On⁹ account credentials.
- At any time the user can check the status of his/her orders through the user dashboard¹⁰. This dashboard, shown in a table-view, includes the history of service order(s) submitted

⁸ <https://servproject.i3m.upv.es/ec3-ltos/index.php>

⁹ <https://egi.eu/sso>

¹⁰ <https://marketplace.egi.eu/order-history>

by the user since his/her account has been created. For each service order, additional information can be obtained clicking on the “Details” button.

In three working days, the service-order request will be processed by the Operator of the service and the user will be informed via email about the outcome of this evaluation.

In case the service order is accepted by the operator of the service:

- The user can login to the Elastic Cloud Compute Cluster (EC3) portal and configure the virtual cluster with the related tools and applications to be deployed on top of Infrastructure as a Service (IaaS). The cluster, which is defined with a 'job wizard' interface for the user (Fig. 1, 2), is composed by a front node, where a batch job scheduler is running, and a number of compute nodes. These compute nodes will be dynamically deployed and provisioned to fit increasing load, and un-deployed when they are in idle status. The installation and configuration of the cluster is performed by means of the execution of Ansible receipts.

Figure 1. Deployment of virtual clusters on Exoscale.

Figure 3. The EC3 job wizard to configuration the virtual cluster.

- Every six months the user is invited to report feedback from the successful applicant.
- The user MUST acknowledge the EOSC-hub and the HNSciCloud projects in the scientific publications/presentations benefiting from the service. The following acknowledgement statement can be used for this purpose: **“This work used the EGI Applications on Demand service, which is co-funded by the EOSC-hub project (grant number 777536). The HNSciCloud project (grant number 687614) is also sponsoring the service, allowing users to access the HNSciCloud services pilot for limited scale usage using the voucher scheme provided by Exoscale”.**

2.1.3.2. Additional feedback from external users

As an alternative means of consuming vouchers outside the EOSC marketplace, a small number of early adopters outside the project consortia have been invited to use the vouchers distributed by Exoscale and T-Systems. The access to the cloud services has been performed directly in a self-service manner without any intermediaries. The overall feedback collected were very positive. During the trial, students managed to redeem the vouchers, and use the pilot services for computational analysis without the need of support. The workflow to redeem the vouchers, access the pilot services and monitor the voucher credit through the Grafana dashboard was clear.

3. Summary

Several training and consultancy events, organized during the second part of the pilot phase, contributed to open the resulting hybrid platform to a wide range of potential users, including the “long-tail” of science users. These events were hosted by members of the Buyers Group with the training and consultancy provided by the contractors according to the needs of the host. The HNSciCloud training events have been delivered to target the requirements and needs of different stakeholders including end-users, developers and system administrators.